

BIODIVERSITY AND IMPORTANCE OF PREDATORY BEETLES IN THE SURKHANDARYA REGION

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Abstract: This article highlights the natural and geographical conditions, climatic features of the Surkhandarya region, as well as the biodiversity of predatory beetles common in this area, and their importance in the natural control of agricultural pests.

Keywords: predator beetles, Coleoptera, ground beetles (Carabidae), Staphylinidae (Staphylinidae), Coccellanidae (Coccinellidae), biological protection, beetles (Meloidae).

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Surxondaryo viloyatining tabiiy-geografik sharoiti, iqlim xususiyatlari hamda ushbu hududda tarqalgan yirtqich qo'ng'izlarning biologik xilma-xilligi va ularning qishloq xo'jaligi zararkunandalariga qarshi tabiiy kurashdagi ahamiyati yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Yirtqich qo'ng'izlar, *Coleoptera*, vizildoq qo'ng'izlar (*Carabidae*), stafilinidlar (*Staphylinidae*), xonqizi qo'ng'izlar (*Coccinellidae*), biologik himoya, malxamchi qo'ng'izlar- (*Meloidae*).

Аннотация: В данной статье освещаются природно-географические условия, климатические особенности Сурхандарьинской области, а также биоразнообразие хищных жуков, распространенных на данной территории, и их значение в естественной борьбе с сельскохозяйственными вредителями. **Ключевые слова:** жуки - хищники, жесткокрылые, жуки-жужелице (*Carabidae*), Стафилиниды (*Staphylinidae*), кокцеланиды (*Coccinellidae*), биологическая защита, жуки нарывники- (*Meloidae*).

Introduction. The Surkhandarya region is a part of the Republic of Uzbekistan characterized by its unique geographical location and natural conditions. Due to its geographic position, the region possesses distinctive natural-geographical features; in particular, it is located in the southernmost part of Uzbekistan. The region includes the Surkhan-Sherabad valley and the surrounding mountain systems.

Surkhandarya borders Tajikistan to the east and northeast via the Bobotog and Hissar mountain ranges, Kashkadarya region to the northwest through the Chakchar and Boysun mountains, and Turkmenistan to the west along the watershed of the Kohitang Mountains. In the south, the state border runs along the Amu Darya River, separating the region from Afghanistan.

The territory of the region encompasses several botanical-geographical districts, including Boysun, Bobotog, Kohitang, Sangardak-Topalang, and Surkhan-Sherabad. This area is distinguished by high taxonomic diversity and richness in rare, endemic, and relict species [5].

Therefore, the aim of this study is to investigate the biodiversity of predatory beetles distributed across different parts of the Surkhandarya region and to assess their importance in regulating populations of agricultural pests.

The order Coleoptera (beetles) is the largest order in terms of species diversity. Their feeding specialization is extremely diverse: most are phytophagous, including many serious plant pests, while others include entomophagous, necrophagous, saprophagous, and coprophagous species. In biological plant protection, representatives of the families such as ground beetles (Carabidae), rove beetles (Staphylinidae), lady beetles (Coccinellidae), and soft-bodied beetles play a particularly important role. Compared to parasitoids, many of them are predators [8,9,11,13,22,24].

Research Methods. Scientific studies were conducted during 2023–2025 in various areas of the Surkhandarya region using commonly applied methods in entomology and agricultural entomology, including observation, comparison, and experimental approaches.

Phenological and faunistic investigations were carried out based on the methodological guidelines developed by A. Qulmamatov [25].

Research Results. Family Carabidae (Ground Beetles). Ground beetles (Carabidae) occupy one of the leading positions among beetles in terms of species richness and play an important role in reducing populations of harmful insects in ecosystems. They are active, mostly dark-colored, sometimes brightly colored beetles.

Their antennae are setaceous or filiform, and their legs are adapted for running, with all tarsi consisting of five segments. Typically, these beetles inhabit the soil surface or its upper layers and exhibit nocturnal activity. Their larvae are campodeiform and live in the soil.

Most species of ground beetles are effective predators in both larval and adult (imago) stages. For example, some species belonging to the genera *Sebia* and *Brachinus* are ectoparasites during the larval stage, developing on the surface of larvae and pupae of harmful insects [9,25].

Adult beetles mainly lead a predatory lifestyle. However, larvae of some species feed on decomposing plant residues and actively participate in soil formation processes.

According to Ye.S. Sugonyaev and K. Kamalov (1976), *Microlestes plagiatus* feeds on first- to third-instar larvae of the cotton bollworm. Observations by K.V. Arnoldi (1947) showed that *Carabus fetschekoi* significantly reduced populations of overwintering bugs in the Kashkadarya region. Data from B.P. Adashkevich and A. Dadamirzayev (1981) indicate that in Uzbekistan, ground beetles belonging to the genera *Cicindela*, *Calosoma*, *Carabus*, *Scarites*, *Broscus*, *Bembidion*, and *Pterostichus* play a major role in controlling harmful insects [1,2,4,6,17].

According to our observations, in the mountainous and foothill areas of the Surkhandarya region, *Calosoma sycophanta* is widely distributed, while in steppe and desert zones, species such as *Scarites bucida*, *Lebia menetriesi*, *Microlestes plagiatus*, and *Carabus fetschekoi* are more common compared to other species.

Family Meloidae (Blister Beetles). More than 4,000 species of this family are known worldwide, with nearly 100 species recorded in Uzbekistan. Adult beetles feed on flowers and sometimes leaves of plants. During mass outbreaks, they can cause significant damage to pasture vegetation and rainfed crops. However, in the larval stage, they are not harmful; instead, they act as entomophages by parasitizing grasshopper egg pods.

Based on our observations, three species of blister beetles were recorded: *Mylabris frolovi* Germ. (Frolov's blister beetle), *Mylabris quadripunctata* L. (four-spotted blister beetle), and *Zonitis flava* F. (yellow blister beetle). These species are mainly distributed in mountainous and foothill pastures, while they occur very rarely in sandy desert pastures.

For instance, they were found to be widely and moderately distributed in the pastures of Boysun, Oltinsoy, and Uzun districts, as well as in the Gulbahor area of Termez district in the Surkhandarya region. In contrast, they were recorded in very low numbers in the Olapar, Navruz, and Kallamozor areas of Sherabad district; the Sayxon and Lalmiqor massifs of Kumkurgan district; and the Lalmiqor areas of Shurchi and Sariosiyo districts.

The main reason for this distribution pattern is that these areas are historical breeding foci of gregarious locusts. Regular chemical treatments, primarily against the Moroccan locust, are carried out annually in these regions. As a result, along with harmful locusts, many other insect species are also eliminated.

Family Staphylinidae (Rove Beetles). Members of this family are distinguished by their elongated and narrow bodies and very short elytra. During movement, they often bend their abdomen upwards or forwards.

Their larvae are campodeiform with a well-developed prognathous head. Both adults and larvae inhabit leaf litter, under stones, beneath tree bark, in riverbank sands, as well as in nests of mammals and birds, and in ant and termite colonies [20,21].

Most species are predators, while some are parasitic; additionally, saprophagous, coprophagous, and necrophagous forms are also found among staphylinids. In cotton agrobiocenoses, about 10 predatory species occur, including *Philonthus concinnus*, *Ph. politus*, and others, which prey on soil-dwelling insects and sometimes aphids.

Family Coccinellidae (Lady Beetles). Representatives of this family are widely distributed and play a crucial role in controlling dangerous agricultural pests. These include aphids, mites, caterpillars, scale insects, eggs and early instars of Lepidoptera, as well as larvae of *Phytonomus*. More than 4,500 species of coccinellids are known worldwide, of which over 200 species have been recorded in CIS countries. In Central Asia, about 180 species occur, and in Uzbekistan, 106 species and subspecies belonging to 25 genera and 2 subfamilies have been identified. Approximately 80 of these are known as entomophages [2,4,6,8,11,12,13,16,18,19,20,22,23].

Under the conditions of the Surkhandarya region, the following lady beetle species are dominant in cotton and other agricultural crops:

- *Coccinella septempunctata* L. (seven-spotted lady beetle)
- *Stethorus punctillum* Ws. (spotted *Stethorus*)
- *Adonia variegata* Goeze (variegated lady beetle) [14,15]

Lady beetles typically have a rounded, dome-shaped body with a convex dorsal surface and a flattened underside, often resembling a hemisphere.

Their eggs are yellow, relatively large, and elongated. Newly laid eggs may appear pale grayish due to the visible larval body through the chorion [9,11,15]. Females usually lay eggs in clusters on different parts of plants near aphid colonies. Upon hatching, larvae immediately begin feeding on aphids.

Larvae hatch rapidly and synchronously. Initially, they remain clustered on the egg shells for a short period before dispersing to locate prey. Younger larvae are less mobile, but mobility increases significantly with age, allowing them to move between aphid colonies.

Before pupation, larvae attach themselves to a substrate using the posterior part of their body. Newly emerged adults actively prey on aphids and begin mating after 10–12 days. Egg-laying starts 1–2 days after mating. Females do not lay eggs continuously; peak oviposition (38–42 eggs per day) occurs 10–15 days after the onset of egg-laying. Toward the end of the oviposition

period, eggs are laid at intervals of 1–2 days. The oviposition period can last up to 45 days, with a single female laying between 250 and 2,900 eggs in total [15].

Lady beetles overwinter in the adult stage in mountainous areas at various elevations.

Among the most effective species for biological control are the seven-spotted lady beetle (*Coccinella septempunctata*), the two-spotted lady beetle (*Adalia bipunctata*), and the specialized predator of spider mites, *Stethorus punctillum* [16,17,18].

In cotton agrobiocenoses, lady beetles (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) can reduce populations of alfalfa aphids by 50–60% and melon aphids by 10–15% in spring. Species such as *Coccinella septempunctata*, *Adonia variegata*, and *Propylea quatuordecimpunctata*, as well as *Scymnus frontalis* and *Coccinella undecimpunctata*, significantly suppress aphid populations.

In addition to aphids, lady beetles also feed on mites, scale insects, and the eggs and early instars of various pests [18,2]. According to Mamatov K.Sh. (2024), *Coccinella septempunctata* develops in greenhouse conditions and feeds on aphids damaging plants, reducing their populations by up to 50–60%.

Conclusion. Predatory beetles are key natural enemies of agricultural pests and play an essential ecological role in regulating pest populations. The warm and dry subtropical climate, fertile soils, and unique natural–geographical conditions of the Surkhandarya region create a favorable environment for the widespread distribution of predatory beetles, particularly representatives of the families Carabidae, Staphylinidae, and Coccinellidae.

These entomophages contribute directly to the healthy development of crops by maintaining pest populations under control in agrobiocenoses. A deeper understanding of the biology and ecology of predatory beetles, along with the creation of optimal conditions for their reproduction and the conservation of their natural habitats, will enhance biological control systems in agriculture.

This approach will reduce the reliance on pesticides and serve as an important factor in ensuring ecological sustainability and high agricultural productivity.

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